

PARTIAL REPLACEMENT OF CEMENT WITH MARBLE DUST POWDER, FINE AGGREGATE WITH COPPER SLAG, AND COARSE AGGREGATE WITH RECYCLED AGGREGATE IN CONCRETE

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ABSTRACT

Construction companies generate non-biodegradable waste that harms the environment. However, incorporating this waste into concrete can support sustainable and eco-friendly construction practices. The present investigations study the partial replacement of binder materials such as cement with marble dust powder (MDP), fine aggregate with copper slag (CPS), and coarse aggregate with recycled aggregate concrete (RAC), when substituted for coarse aggregate, to analyze concrete mechanical properties. A constant percentage of marble dust powder was added to replace the binder material (cement). Additionally, copper slag replaced 10%, 20%, and 30% of the fine aggregate, and recycled aggregate replaced 10%, 20%, and 30% of the coarse aggregate. According to the M-30 standard, Specimens' compressive, tensile, and flexural strengths were evaluated for (7, 14, & 28) days after cure, respectively. These additives can improve concrete's mechanical characteristics. Thus, these materials have the potential to serve as alternatives to conventional construction materials through partial replacement.

KEYWORDS

Concrete, Marble Dust Powder, Copper Slag, Recycled Aggregate, & Strength.

1. INTRODUCTION

The second most commonly used substance on earth is concrete, which is produced annually at a rate of 25 billion metric tonnes. Its many applications include infrastructure development, low- and high-rise construction, military facilities, municipal projects, and many more. The primary constituents of concrete comprise cement, aggregates, water, and admixtures. The ever-increasing demand has led to the depletion of these resources. Human intervention threatens aggregate accessibility for future generations as more than 1 billion metric tonnes of construction waste and destruction are created annually [1]. Recent years have seen an increase in industrial waste production, creating challenges in waste management. In some industries, untreated waste is discharged into rivers and lakes or disposed of in open fields. It is critical to emphasize that these actions represent a serious hazard to aquatic life and social health [2]. Maximizing the sustainable use of available resources is one way to minimize material shortages and ensure efficient management. To accomplish this, waste materials or by-products can be used to partially replace the virgin resources so that they can be effective and economical simultaneously.

This is crucial since 300 million metric tonnes of building and demolition trash are recycled each year in the U.S. [3], [4]. They found that recycled concrete aggregates absorb more water than natural aggregates. However, concrete containing 50% RCA has similar compressive strength to ordinary concrete. After RCA is replaced with 25–30% concrete, its tensile strength remains high. The compressive strength of concrete combined built through recycled aggregates, river sand, and 42% coarse aggregates was 30.17 MPa after 28 days. Copper slag, a by-product manufactured by copper manufacturing, produces approximately 2.2 metric tonnes for every tonne of copper ore. Globally, copper slag production is projected to be a total of 24.6 million metric tonnes [5], [6], [7]. Utilizing copper slag instead of fine aggregate can increase M25-grade concrete strength by up to 100%. Fly ash was also used to substitute cement at 30% and 50%, respectively. When copper slag was substituted for fine aggregate, concrete's compressive strength increased by 100%. After replacing copper slag with 10%, 15%, 20%, 25%, 30%, and 35%, concrete specimens replaced with copper slag demonstrated an increase in compressive strength of 10% to 30% compared with conventional specimens. However, compressive strength decreases as copper content rises [8].

Marble dust is generated during marble cutting, polishing, or shaping. Marble stone is converted into dust in this process to the extent of a 20–25% loss [9], [10]. Marble dust powder was utilized in various percentages of 0%, 5%, 10%, and 20%. Each mix used 0.43 water to cement. The samples' compression, tensile, and flexural strengths were evaluated for seven, fourteen, and twenty-eight days. Mixing marble dust powder (MDP) instead of cement showed a 10% improvement in the concrete's compression strength. Concrete's flexural and tensile strengths were increased by 15% and 15%, respectively, when a cement substitute (MDP) was used [11]. Marble powder improves workability and compaction, as excessive cement can cause segregation and bleeding, weakening concrete. Concrete compressive strength increased by 25% when 5% of the cement was replaced with MDP. Additionally, marble powder replaced 7.5% of cement and showed an 8% improvement [12].

Research significance

This research investigated how the inclusion of marble dust powder, copper slag, and recycled concrete aggregate would impact concrete properties. In this experiment, the binder material (cement) was replaced in part by marble dust powder at a constant ratio of 10%, copper slag was substituted for fine aggregate in varying proportions of 10%, 20%, and 30%, and recycled aggregate was replaced with the same percentages of 10%, 20%, and 30% of coarse aggregate. Conplast SP430 superplasticizer was utilized to treat 1.1% of cement throughout the study, and a W/C ratio was fixed at 0.4. Concrete compressive strength was calculated by applying cube-shaped specimens' measurements of (150 * 150 * 150) mm. The split strength was determined using a (150 * 300) mm cylinder. The flexural strength of a beam (100 * 100 * 500) mm was evaluated. The samples were evaluated 7, 14, and 28 days after moulding and curing.

2. MATERIALS

2.1. Cement.

Cement was implemented as a binding substance during the experimental evaluation of OPC 43-grade cement in accordance with IS 8112:2013 [13]. It was locally available in Chandigarh, India.

2.2. Superplasticizer.

An admixture based on poly naphthalene sulphonate is utilized to enhance high-strength concrete workability. This study utilized Conplast SP-430 as a chemical admixture, according to IS 9103-1999 [14].

2.3. Fine Aggregates.

Crushed gravel is reached over a 4.75 mm curtain to produce sand. According to IS 383:1970 [15], this sand is classified as zone III. It was procured locally from Chandigarh, India.

2.4. Coarse Aggregates.

Coarse aggregate is made up of crushed rocks and natural gravels with 10 mm and 20 mm thicknesses. It is readily available in Chandigarh, India.

2.5. Marble Dust Powder.

When marble stones are cut, polished, and sharpened, 20 to 25 percent of the debris produced is MDP [9], [10], as shown in Figure 1 and Table 1, which list its chemical composition. It was procured locally from Jai Mata Marble House, Zirakpur Patiala Road, Mohali, India.

Fig 1. Marble dust powder

Table 1: The chemical composition of (MDP)

Sr. No	properties	% value
01.	CaO	32.23%
02.	SiO ₂	4.99 %
03.	Al ₂ O ₃	1.09 %
04.	Fe ₂ O ₃	1.09 %
05.	MgO	18.94 %
06.	SO ₃	0.02 %
07.	K ₂ O	0.91%
08.	Na ₂ O	0.63%
0.9	LOI	40.63%

2.6. Copper slag.

By-products from copper production are copper slag. Copper production results in around 2.2 tonnes of copper slag per copper tonne [5],[6]. Globally, copper industry slag production and its chemical composition exceed 24.6 million tonnes [16], as indicated in Figure 2 and Table 2.

Figure 2. Copper slag

Table 2. Chemical composition of (CPS)

Sr. No	properties	% value
01.	TiO ₂	0.41
02.	Mn ₂ O ₃	0.22
03.	CuO	1.12
04.	K ₂ O	2.62
05.	SiO ₂	37.26
06.	Na ₂ O	0.58
07.	CaO	2.38
08.	Al ₂ O ₃	3.95
09.	Fe ₂ O ₃	68.29
10.	SO ₃	2.75

2.7. Recycled aggregate concrete.

Recycled aggregate concrete is made by breaking and processing aged asphalt, which is then reused in existing building projects. In this way, crushed concrete can be used instead of virgin aggregates [3], as shown in Figure 3 and Table 3, and its physical properties. It was procured in 10mm and 20mm sizes from the C&D plant in Chandigarh, India.

Fig 3. Recycled aggregate concrete

Table 3: Physical characteristics of recycled aggregate.

Sr. No	Physical	value
01.	Bulk Density (km/m^3)	1650
02.	Water Absorption (%)	0.3
03.	Fineness Modulus (%)	7.78
04.	S.P Gravity	2.58
05.	Aggregate Crushing Value (%)	36.3
06.	Aggregate Impact Value (%)	35.2

3. Experimental Methodology.

An experimental investigation was conducted using an M30 mix. The study analyzed the behavior of concrete when the partial replacement of binder materials (cement) was done with the MDP. According to previous researchers, MDP was fixed at 10% [17],[10], and [18]. The fine aggregate was substituted with CPS in proportions of 10%, 20%, and 30%, while the coarse aggregate was partially substituted with RA in varying proportions of 10%, 20%, and 30%, respectively. This study investigated concrete's compressive, split-tensile, and flexural strengths. A total of 324 items, including 108 cubes, 108 cylinders, and 108 beams, were cast. After 7, 14, and 28 days, these samples were evaluated.

3.1. Casting of specimens.

Concrete cube compressive strength was evaluated according to IS 516-1959 [19]. Cubes measuring (150 * 150 * 150) mm were molded after curing for seven, fourteen, and twenty-eight days. Additionally, samples with measures of 150 mm * and 300 mm were used to assess split tensile strength in accordance with IS 5816-1999 [20]. To find out the flexural tensile strength of concrete, samples measuring (100 * 100 * 500) mm were tested according to IS 516-1959 [19]. The average of three samples was utilized for analyzing and investigating different concrete mixes.

3.2. Mix Designs.

The M30 concrete mix designs were developed based on IS 10262:2019 [21] for various mix groups. The control concrete utilized a cement-water ratio of 0.4, based on Table 4. All mixtures were manually prepared on a non-absorbent surface. The process involved mixing sand, cement, MDP, and CPS, followed by adding coarse aggregates and RAC. The components were thoroughly mixed with a shovel until they were homogeneous. The concrete mixture was then prepared by adding water and a superplasticizer. The mixture was then consolidated within a mould using a tabletop vibrator. The specimens were removed 24 hours after casting from the molds. Curing took place in a water tank maintained at 29°C.

Table 4. Mix designs of materials calculations.

Mix	MDP (kg/m ³)	CPS (kg/m ³)	RCA (kg/m ³)	Cement (kg/m ³)	F.A (kg/m ³)	C.A (kg/m ³)	Water (kg/m ³)	Admixture (kg/m ³)
Control	0	0	0	48.6	97.43	131.85	19.44	0
MCR 1	4.857	9.75	13.24	43.74	87.75	118.69	17.51	0.5
MCR 2	4.857	9.75	26.412	43.74	87.75	105.45	17.51	0.5
MCR 3	4.857	9.75	39.56	43.74	87.75	92.3	17.51	0.5
MCR 4	4.857	19.5	13.24	43.74	77.99	118.69	17.51	0.5
MCR 5	4.857	19.5	26.41	43.74	77.99	105.45	17.51	0.5
MCR 6	4.857	19.5	39.56	43.74	77.99	92.28	17.51	0.5
MCR 7	4.857	29.24	13.24	43.74	68.3	118.69	17.51	0.5
MCR 8	4.857	29.24	26.412	43.74	68.3	105.45	17.51	0.5
MCR 9	4.857	29.24	39.56	43.74	68.3	92.3	17.51	0.5

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION.

4.1. Workability.

A slump test was performed in accordance with IS 1199:1959 [22], to determine concrete workability. The study investigated the effects of partially replacing binder materials in the concrete mix. Specifically, cement was replaced with MDP, fine aggregate with CPS, and coarse material with RAC. Slump values increased as RCA ratios increased, as seen in Figure 4. Comparing the slump values, the control concrete had a slump value of 20.5 cm, while the MCR1, MCR2, MCR3, MCR4, MCR5, MCR6, MCR7, MCR8, and MCR9 samples had slump values of 21.9 cm, 23.5 cm, 26 cm, 21.5 cm, 23 cm, 25.4 cm, 21.1 cm, 22.5 cm, and 24.8 cm, respectively. However, it was also observed that a lower proportion of CPS was associated with a greater slump value than a higher proportion. This observation was particularly evident in the concrete sample (MCR3), which contained 10% MDP, 10% CPS, and 30% RAC. This could be attributed to the (MDP) improvement in the compactness and density of the slump value and (CPS) utilization with its angular grain shape and size. When (RA) is present, it increases its slump value due to aggregate texture, grading, and mix proportions. This results in increased surface area and improved bonding within the concrete mixture because of the low water content of the superplasticizer.

Figure 4. Results of slump cone test.

4.2. Compressive strength.

This section aims to study the impact of partially substituting concrete binders, such as cement with MDP, fine aggregate with CPS, and coarse aggregate with RA, on concrete compression strength characteristics. The compression strength was evaluated according to IS 516:1959 [19] after specimens had been cured for 7, 14, and 28 days. The results displayed a notable rise in compression strength compared to the control mix. Specifically, the strengths were measured at 27.07 N/mm², 30.57 N/mm², and 34.33 N/mm² for the respective curing durations. In contrast, the control mix displayed strengths of 23.97 N/mm², 27.5 N/mm², and 31.13 N/mm². This indicates an improvement of 12.97%, 11.16%, and 10.27% for the corresponding curing periods. Figure 5 presents these findings. These results were obtained with a constant proportion of 10% MDP, 30% CPS, and 10% RA in the concrete mixture (MCR7). Including MDP in the concrete formulation positively influences compressive strength and durability. When SiO₂ reacts with calcium Ca(OH)₂, calcium silicate hydrate forms. These compounds enhance the chemical stability of concrete and contribute to increased strength. Additionally, the fine-grained particles of MDP improve the compactness and density of the concrete mixture. A superplasticizer cut the volume of water in concrete, makes it easier to place, and increases its durability and strength. Combined with a lower W/C ratio, this leads to a more solid cement paste with fewer lumps and voids, consequently resulting in higher compressive strength. Incorporating CPS particles in the concrete mixture enhances the bounding density and reduces permeability. The angular shape of CPS particles increases their surface area and promotes better cohesion within the concrete. Moreover, the addition of sharp-edged waste copper slag particles further improves concrete bonding characteristics. However, the utilization of recycled aggregate (RA) in concrete tends to decrease its strength because of variables like maximum water absorption, irregular shapes and sizes, low RA strength, and weak mortar formation.

Figure 5. Comprehensive Strength (MPa).

4.3. Split tensile strength.

Concrete split tensile strengths were evaluated according to IS 516:1999 [20]. This experiment aimed to compare the effects of partially substituting binders, such as cement with MDP, fine aggregate with CPS, and coarse aggregate with RA, on the split tensile strength of concrete for (7, 14, and 28) days. These results indicated that concrete reached its maximum split tensile strength at these respective curing durations. Specifically, the strengths were measured at 2.4 N/mm², 3.08 N/mm², and 3.65 N/mm². These values represent a significant increase of 42.85%, 46.66%, and 17.74% compared to the control mix, which displayed strengths of 1.68 N/mm², 2.1 N/mm², and 3.1 N/mm², respectively. These results are illustrated in Figure 6. These findings were obtained with a constant proportion of 10% marble dust powder (MDP), 30% copper slag (CPS), and 10% recycled aggregate (RA) in the concrete mixture (MCR7). Split tensile strength gains follow a similar pattern to compressive strength gains. The similarity between the parameter and compression strength is apparent. It can be demonstrated that the optimum value for replacement is also (MCR7) for split tensile strength.

Fig 6. Split tensile strength (MPa).

4.4. Flexural strength.

The flexural strength of the concrete was assessed following the guidelines of IS 516:1959 [19]. This study aimed to investigate the impact of partially substituting binders, such as cement with MDP, fine aggregate with CPS, and coarse aggregate with RA, on concrete flexural strength for (7, 14, and 28) days. The results signified that the concrete carries out its highest flexural strength at these respective curing durations, with measurements of 4.22 N/mm², 5.32 N/mm², and 5.68 N/mm². These values represent a significant increase of 13.44%, 23.43%, and 14.05% compared to the control mix, which displayed strengths of 3.72 N/mm², 4.31 N/mm², and 4.98 N/mm², respectively. Figure 7 illustrates it visually. Although flexural strength gains are not as dramatic as compressive strength gains, the patterns are similar. The correlation between the parameter and compression strength is evident. It can be well established that the optimum value for replacement is also (MCR7) for flexural strength.

Figure 7. Flexure Strength.

5. Conclusion.

1. Concrete slump values increased with increasing percentages of RAC into the concrete mix for fixed MDP and varying CPS proportions. (MCR3).
2. The addition of MDP and CPS to concrete enhances compressive strength, flexural strength, and split tensile strength. However, its strength is reduced by the addition of RA.
3. The maximum compression, tensile, and flexural strengths calculated compared to the neutral mixture were found at 10% MDP (constant), 30% CPS, and 10% RAC (MCR7), which can be considered an optimum percentage for this research.
4. It is concluded that 10% MDP can be substituted for cement in concrete and 30% CPS can be substituted for fine aggregate in order to enhance the achievement characteristics of concrete.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

It was a great privilege to conduct this research under the guidance of Professor Shalika Mehta. Working with her at Chandigarh University was a pleasure, and I am grateful for her unwavering support, guidance, and encouragement.

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